

LABIAL FRENECTOMY USING ELECTROCAUTERY: A MODERN APPROACH TO A TRADITIONAL PROCEDURE – A CASE REPORT

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ABSTARCT:

An aberrant frenal attachment is associated with various problems such as gingival recession, persistence of midline diastema, esthetic compromise and difficulty in maintaining oral hygiene. This case report demonstrates a successful management of the aberrant maxillary labial frenum after orthodontic treatment to prevent relapse of midline diastema and improve esthetics of the patient with excision of frenum with electrosurgery. Many benefits of electrocautery over conventional technique using scalpel are minimal bleeding, minimal pain, little or no postoperative scar and better healing. A 16 year old female patient was treated with maxillary labial frenectomy using electrocautery and follow up results showed uneventful healing and no post-operative complications thus emphasizing the use of newer techniques such as electrocautery for frenectomy for better results and patient compliance.

INTRODUCTION

Frenum can be defined as “a fibrous band of tissue attached to the bone of the mandible and maxillae, and is commonly superficial to the muscle attachments.” Median maxillary labial frenum also known as Sewerin’s frenum or the frenulum labii superioris is a mucous membrane fold containing connective tissue and muscle fibres that attaches lip to the alveolar mucosa, the gingiva und underlying periosteum.¹⁻³ Aberrant frenal attachment is associated with problems such as persistence of midline diastema, gingival recession, compromised esthetics and difficulty in maintaining oral hygiene.⁴ Surgical excision of maxillary labial frenum has been suggested to prevent orthodontic relapse of midline diastema.⁵ Maxillary labial frenum has been classified by Placek et al as

- a. mucosal attachment of the frenum, means an attachment of the frenum to the mucogingival junction.
- b. gingival attachment, stands for an attachment of the frenum to the attached gingiva.
- c. papillary attachment, means an attachment of the frenum to the papilla.
- d. papillary penetrating attachment is in those cases when the attachment of the frenum passes right up to the papilla, while inserting in attached gingiva.⁶

Frenectomy is the complete removal of the frenum, including its attachment to the underlying bone, while *frenotomy* is the incision and the relocation of the frenal attachment.⁷ Various methods used for frenectomy include use of scalpel, electrocautery and lasers. The scalpel method include a conventional technique where a diamond shaped defect is formed, Miller,s technique, Paralleling technique, Z- plasty and V-Y plasty.^{2,4} Each method has its own advantages and disadvantages where use of scalpel techniques are associated with less patient compliance, bleeding, scar tissue formation, loss of papilla and high relapse rate.^{2,4,8}

Electrosurgery has been defined as the intentional passage of high-frequency waveforms, or currents through the tissues of the body to achieve a controllable surgical effect. By varying the mode of application of

this type of current, the clinician can use electrosurgery for cutting or coagulating soft tissues.² Electrosurgery leads to minimal procedural bleeding and there is no need of sutures and the healing occurs by secondary intention. Curved electrodes aid visibility and thus they are efficient and effective for soft tissue removal.⁴ Clinical studies have shown that electrosurgery used for frenectomy provide better patient perception in terms of postoperative pain and function than that achieved using the scalpel technique.⁹

CASE REPORT

A 16-year-old female patient was referred from the Department of Orthodontics after orthodontic treatment to the Department of Oral and maxillofacial surgery with the chief complaint of abnormal frenum attachment. The patient was diagnosed with a frenal attachment of papillary type.

The patient was advised a frenectomy procedure. The patient had a fear about the blade and bleeding, therefore, the procedure was carried out with the electrocautery unit. Informed written consent was taken and haematological examinations were carried out, which were normal and within ranges.

After the area was anaesthetized with local infiltration by using 2% lignocaine with 1:80000 adrenaline, the surgical procedure was carried out using an electrocautery unit, the frenum was held with the haemostat and by using a needle electrode tip, it was excised. The incision was given above and below the undersurface of the haemostat and wedge-shaped tissue was excised. No sutures were placed.

Figure 1- Pre-operative view showing abnormal frenum attachment which was of papillary type.

Figure 2- The haemostat was held engaging the abnormal frenum

Figure 3- Excision of frenum with electrocautery

Figure 4- A wedge-shaped triangular tissue was surgically excised by electrocautery

Figure 5- Post-operative picture showing diamond-shape incision after performing frenectomy with electrocautery with haemostasis achieved

Figure 6- Post-operative view after 7 days showing satisfactory healing and no signs of infection

Figure 7- Post-operative view after 1 month showing complete and satisfactory healing and less scar formation

Figure 5 shows a post-operative view after frenectomy where the bleeding did not occur and a diamond shaped frenum incision line can be seen.

The patient was reviewed after 3 days, 7 days and 1 month for periodic recall appointments. The Visual analogue score (VAS Score) for measurement of pain was recorded immediately after surgery, on 3rd day and on 7th day.¹⁰ It was 1, 0 and 0 immediately after surgery, on 3rd day and on 7th day respectively.

The 7th day post-operative picture in Figure 6 shows satisfactory healing, and the patient reported no discomfort and pain.

Figure 7 shows complete satisfactory healing, less scar formation and resulted in favourable outcomes for the treatment at 1 month follow up.

DISCUSSION

The maxillary labial frenum is formed by the ectolabial bands that connect the palatine papilla to the tubercle of the upper lip as a post-eruptive remnant. It is considered pathogenic when the frenum is abnormally large or lacks a prominent attachment zone to the gingiva along the midline.¹¹

The conventional method of frenectomy was first described by Archer (1961) and Kruger (1964).¹² A scar and longitudinal incision with unaesthetic appearance along with bleeding and patient compliance are some of the drawbacks of this conventional technique which are especially evident with development of newer techniques such as laser and electrosurgery.^{2,12} Diode lasers have also been used for the frenectomy which provide bloodless surgical field, faster healing and minimal pain but are costly as compared to the electrocautery.^{9,13} Electrocautery offers bloodless field, no need of sutures, minimal pain, little or no scar formation, patient compliance and comparatively less cost as compared to laser.^{2,4,9,11} A case report by Dias CP et al showed similar results.²

Two main types of electrosurgical units used in dentistry are monopolar and bipolar. A bipolar unit is characterized by an arrangement in which two electrodes are positioned very close. An individual wire carries current from a monopolar device to the surgical site, and the device has just one electrode. For grounding, a pad must be placed on the patient's back. Hence, as the electrical current flows from one electrode to the other without a grounding pad, bipolar units are more expensive than diode lasers and monopolar units. As bipolar units have two wires, it results in a less precise cut when compared to its monopolar unit.¹¹ In this case, a monopolar electrocautery was used.

The electrosurgery showed lesser time for incision and excision as compared to CO2 laser.¹¹ Thus, electrosurgery offers better prospects to the patient in terms of surgical experience and healing. Further studies are needed to compare frenectomy by using electrocautery with other techniques.

CONCLUSION

This case demonstrates removal of maxillary labial frenum by using electrocautery with uneventful healing, minimal pain and no scar formation. This treatment demonstrates functional and esthetic improvement after orthodontic treatment with excision of maxillary labial frenum. Further studies comparing various other methods of frenectomy with electrocautery in terms of healing, pain perception and patient compliance are required.

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There is no conflict of interest.

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